

Strong Metal-Adsorbate Interactions Increase the Reactivity and Decrease the Orientational Order of OH- functionalized N-Heterocyclic Carbene Monolayers

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Abstract

Fundamental understanding of the correlation between the structure and reactivity of chemically-addressable N-Heterocyclic Carbene molecules (NHCs) is essential for the design of functional NHC-based self-assembled monolayers (SAMs). In this work we identified the ways by which the deposition of chemically-addressable OH-NHCs on Au (111) or Pt (111) surfaces modified the anchoring geometry and chemical reactivity of surface-anchored NHCs. The properties of surface-anchored NHCs were probed by conducting X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) and polarized Near-edge X-ray Absorption Fine Structures (NEXAFS) measurements. While no preferred orientation was identified for OH-NHCs on Pt (111), the anchored molecules adopted a preferred flat-lying position on Au (111). Dehydrogenation and aromatization of the imidazoline ring along with partial hydroxyl oxidation were detected in OH-NHCs that were anchored on Au (111). The dehydrogenation and aromatization reactions were facilitated, along with partial decomposition, for OH-NHCs that were anchored on Pt (111). The spectroscopic results reveal that stronger metal-adsorbate interactions increase the reactivity of surface-anchored OH-NHCs while decreasing their molecular orientational order.

Introduction

The strong affinity of N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) to coinage metals enables their self-assembly into monolayers on various metal surfaces.¹⁻⁷ NHC-based self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) show higher thermal and chemical stability in comparison to that of thiol-based SAMs.^{8,9} The improved stability of NHC-based SAMs have led to their utilization in a wide range of applications, from catalysis to biosensing and surface patterning.⁹⁻¹¹

A significant advantage of NHCs over other surface ligands (i.e. thiols and silanes) is their wide chemical tunability.⁵ Electron withdrawing or donating groups can be installed on the two nitrogen atoms of the NHC's ring for tuning the metal surface properties.^{10,12,13} Chemically-active substituents were coupled to the NHCs for synthesis of chemically-addressable NHCs that were utilized, following their surface-anchoring, as chemical probes, co-catalysts and chemical sensors.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ It should be noted that the anchoring geometry of NHCs is influenced by the properties of the substituents. Bulky side groups, such as phenyl, impose a preferred standing orientation of the NHC's ring while smaller side groups, such as methyl, lead to a preferred flat-lying position of surface-anchored NHCs.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

Understanding the correlations between the anchoring-geometry, thermal-stability and chemical reactivity of addressable NHCs is crucial for their utilization in various applications. However, most of the surface-characterization studies have been focused so far on elucidating the surface properties of NHCs that were functionalized with chemically inert substituents¹⁷⁻¹⁹, while analysis of the properties of addressable NHCs was seldom performed.^{1,20-22}

Herein, the influence of Au (111) and Pt (111) surfaces on the anchoring geometry and chemical reactivity of OH-functionalized NHCs (OH-NHCs) were identified by conducting X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and polarized near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) measurements. Similar OH-NHCs were utilized by us and others as chemical

probes^{20,23} and co-catalysts.¹⁶ Surface-sensitive spectroscopic measurements enabled to identify that OH-NHCs adopted a flat-lying orientation on Au (111) surface, while no preferred orientation was detected on Pt (111) surface. Differences were also obtained in the chemical reactivity of OH-NHCs on Pt and Au surfaces. Dehydrogenation and aromatization of the imidazoline ring along with oxidation of the hydroxyl groups were induced once OH-NHCs were anchored on Au (111). Higher tendency toward dehydrogenation and aromatization, coupled with decomposition, were detected for OH-NHCs that were anchored on Pt (111). These results demonstrate that stronger metal-adsorbate interactions on Pt surface, in comparison to that on Au, increased the reactivity of surface-anchored OH-NHCs and decreased their dichroism level.

Experimental

Pt (111) and Au (111) single crystals with a surface area of 0.5 cm² (purchased from SPL) were cleaned under UHV conditions by three consecutive cycles of sputter (1·10⁻⁶ torr Ar; 1.5 keV; 10 minutes) and annealing to 750 and 500 °C for Pt (111) and Au (111), respectively. The cleaning process was validated by C1s XPS measurements.

NHCs were activated in a glove box according to a previously-published protocol (scheme 1).²³ The freshly prepared carbene solution was transferred into a vial and covered the Au (111) or Pt (111) crystals. After 48 h, the crystals were removed from the glove box and intermittently rinsed three times with Tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) and distilled water (5 ml). The samples were then flushed with N₂ for 5 minutes and stored in a glove box. It was previously demonstrated, by comparing the properties of liquid- and vapor-deposited NHCs, that exposure of the sample to atmospheric pressure prior to NHCs' deposition does not substantially influence the surface density of NHCs.²¹

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of surface anchoring of OH-functionalized NHCs on single crystals and the influence of thermal treatment on the aromaticity (KOtBu = Potassium tert-butoxide; THF = Tetrahydrofuran). This scheme describes the chemical properties of the surface-anchored molecules and does not represent their anchoring geometry.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and near-edge X-ray absorption fine structures (NEXAFS) measurements were performed at the ALOISA beamline of the ELETTRA synchrotron facility in Trieste (Italy).²⁴ X-ray absorption measurements were performed in partial electron yield using a channeltron detector equipped with a front grid biased at a negative voltage (-230 V) to filter out the low energy secondary electrons. NEXAFS spectra at the carbon k-edge and the nitrogen k-edge were measured with the resolution set to ~80 meV while keeping the sample at a constant grazing angle of 6°. The orientation of the surface with respect to the photon beam polarization was changed from s-polarization to close to p-polarization by rotating the sample coaxially to the photon beam axis. NEXAFS spectra were reported in the form of a normalized absorption amplitude ($I/I_{\text{reference}}$), using NEXAFS measurement of a clean Au (111) or Pt (111) surfaces as a reference ($I_{\text{reference}}$).²⁴ X-ray photoelectron spectra of C1s, N1s, Pt4f and Au4f were acquired. The binding energies were calibrated according to the core level (4f7/2) position of Au and Pt, located at 84.0 and 71.2 eV, respectively.^{25,26} Analysis of the XPS peaks and their fitting was performed by using CasaXPS software.

Results and discussion

OH-NHCs / Au (111): OH-NHCs were anchored on Au (111) crystal and their properties were characterized by conducting XPS and NEXAFS measurements. N1s XPS signal of the as-

deposited OH-NHCs (Fig. 1a, spectrum i) showed a broad peak (FWHM = 2.4 eV)^{8,27,28} that was fit by two Gaussians, centered at 399.5 eV and 400.8 eV, and assigned to imidazole (aromatic) and imidazoline (non-aromatic) species, respectively.²⁹ The relatively high binding energy of the non-aromatic species was correlated to the partial positive charge of the imidazoline ring.²⁰ The detection of an aromatic species in the XPS spectrum indicated that dehydrogenation and aromatization of the imidazoline backbone has occurred in the as-deposited NHCs. The lack of a dominant high energy (401.5) component in the N1s XPS signal indicated that there is no physisorbed species on the metal surface.³⁰ Herringbone reconstruction was previously demonstrated for gas-phase deposited NHCs on Au (111).^{17,31,9} However, surface reconstruction is not expected in this case since NHCs were deposited under liquid phase conditions.⁸

Fig. 1 XPS (a-b) and polarized NEXAFS (c-d) measurements of OH-NHCs on Au (111). (a) N1s and (b) C1s XPS spectra, along with (c) Nitrogen k-edge and (d) Carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra were measured before (spectra i, black colored) and after annealing of the NHC-coated sample to 200 °C (spectra ii, blue colored). P- and s-polarized NEXAFS spectra were marked by solid and dotted lines, respectively.

The C1s XPS signal of the as-deposited NHCs (Fig. 1b, spectrum i) was fit by three Gaussians, centered at 284.9, 286 and 288.1 eV and assigned to C–C, C–N/C–O and C=O species, respectively.³² The detection of a C=O signature reveals that a fraction of the hydroxyl groups in the as-deposited OH-NHCs were oxidized.²⁰ It was previously demonstrated that both CO-H and O-H vibrations can be detected in surface-anchored OH-NHCs by IR spectroscopy measurements.^{23,20} These results indicate that most of the hydroxyl groups were not deprotonated into alkoxo or oxidized into aldehyde or acid following their surface anchoring, potentially due to steric hindrance.

The XPS peak at 293.5 eV was attributed to the presence of potassium on the surface and originates from residues of potassium tert-butoxide salt that was used for activation of the deprotonation reaction (scheme 1).³³ The detection of potassium on the surface shows that although the sample was rinsed several times following NHCs deposition, this process was not sufficient for complete removal of potassium from the Au surface.

Nitrogen and carbon k-edge NEXAFS measurements (Fig. 1c and 1d, respectively) were conducted to determine the anchoring geometry and chemical properties of OH-NHCs on Au (111) surface. The anchoring geometry of surface-anchored NHCs was deduced by comparing the p- and s-polarized NEXAFS spectra (marked by solid and dotted lines, respectively). Nitrogen k-edge NEXAFS spectra of the as-deposited OH-NHCs (Fig. 1c, spectrum i) displayed a dominant peak at 401.5 eV which was assigned to the imidazoline $N1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{\text{Imidazoline}}$ transition. A minor peak was detected at 399 eV and correlated to aromatic $N1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{\text{Imidazole}}$ transition.²⁹ Continuum of peaks were obtained in the σ^* region (404-415 eV) and attributed to $N1s \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions.²⁹ The amplitude of the $N1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{\text{Imidazoline}}$ transition was higher in the p-polarized spectrum (solid line) than that of the s-polarized spectrum (dotted line). An opposite ratio was obtained in the σ^* region, in which the peaks in the s-polarized spectra were higher than that of the p-polarized

spectra. This dichroism indicates a preference toward a flat-lying orientation of the imidazoline ring of the OH-NHCs on the Au surface.

Several peaks were detected in the carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra of the as-deposited OH-NHCs (Fig 1d, spectrum i). The peak at 285 eV was assigned to aromatic $C1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{(C=N/C=C)}$ transition^{34,29} and the peak at 287.2 eV was attributed to $R^*_{(C-H)}$ transition.³⁵ The presence of an aromatic transition suggests that dehydrogenation reaction occurred at the deposition stage. A shoulder was detected at 289.2 eV and attributed to $C1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{(C=O)}$ transition,³⁵ indicating that the hydroxyl groups were oxidized in part of the surface-anchored OH-NHCs.

The dichroism in the carbon NEXAFS spectra was similar to the one detected in the nitrogen NEXAFS spectra, showing a preference of the surface-anchored molecules towards a flat-lying position on the Au surface (Scheme 2). The two peaks that were detected in the carbon NEXAFS spectra at 297-299 eV (Fig. 1d) were attributed to potassium, which was identified as well in the $C1s$ XPS spectrum (Fig. 1b). Integration of the spectroscopic data reveals that the as-deposited OH-NHCs adopted a preferred flat-lying position on the Au (111) surface. The deposition process led to oxidation of the hydroxyl groups along with dehydrogenation of the imidazoline ring within fraction of the surface-anchored OH-NHCs.

Scheme 2. Schematic illustration of the anchoring geometry of OH-functionalized NHCs on Pt(111) and Au(111) surfaces, as deduced based on polarized NEXAFS measurements.

The OH-NHCs coated Au (111) crystal was annealed to 200 °C and its surface properties were characterized (Fig. 1a-d, spectrum ii). While the N1s XPS peak pattern was maintained after annealing, its peak area has decreased by 30 % (Fig. 1a, spectrum ii). The C1s XPS spectrum showed a similar decrease in the peak intensity following the annealing without any noticeable changes in the peak pattern (Fig. 1b, spectrum ii). It can be therefore deduced that surface annealing facilitated partial desorption of NHCs from the Au surface, with no molecular fragmentation or deformation in the NHCs that remained anchored to the surface. These results demonstrate the thermal stability of NHCs on gold surface in comparison to that of alkanethiols, in which an almost complete removal of the SAM occurred following surface annealing to 200 °C.^{36,37} The amplitude of the potassium XPS signal increased following annealing. This is potentially due to desorption of NHCs from the Au surface that led to improved detection of potassium.

Nitrogen k-edge NEXAFS spectra (Fig. 1c, spectrum ii) showed an increase in the dichroism after annealing, indicating a higher tendency toward a flat lying orientation of the imidazoline ring with respect to the surface. Higher amplitude of the peak at 399 eV was detected in the p-polarized nitrogen NEXAFS spectrum after the thermal treatment, corresponding to higher-degree of dehydrogenation-aromatization reaction of the imidazoline ring.

Carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra displayed a positive dichroic effect following the annealing (Fig. 1d, spectrum ii). In addition, the aromatic transition at 285 eV ($C1s \rightarrow \pi^*_{(C=N/C=C)}$) increased in both polarizations after annealing. This observation is in accordance with the aforementioned N1s XPS and nitrogen k-edge NEXAFS results, which corroborate a prevalent dehydrogenation reaction of the imidazoline backbone at elevated temperatures. Notably, the dehydrogenation of the imidazoline backbone was accompanied by an increase in the NEXAFS dichroism indicating an overall decrease of the average tilt angle. In this regard, we single out two concurring mechanisms: on one side, the bare aromatization of the imidazoline ring favours a flat lying

geometry due to the relatively strong interaction of the aromatic rings with the metal surface charge;³⁸⁻⁴⁰ on the other side, the observed coverage decrease upon annealing determines also a decrease of the intermolecular van der Waal's interactions, further favouring an overall decrease in the average tilt angle, as reported also for other aromatic compounds.^{41,42}

OH-NHCs / Pt (111): OH-NHCs were deposited on Pt (111) to identify the influence of a more chemically-active surface, in comparison to Au (111), on the OH-NHCs stability, reactivity and anchoring geometry. The N1s XPS signal of OH-NHCs on Pt (111) was fit by three Gaussians that were centred at 398, 399.3 and 400.5 eV (Fig. 2a, spectrum i). The two high energy Gaussians at 399.3 and 400.5 eV were assigned to N=C (imidazole) and N-C (imidazoline) species, respectively.^{43,29} The Gaussian centred at 398 eV was correlated to a decomposition pathway of the imidazoline ring on Pt surface.²⁰ This species was not detected in the N1s XPS spectrum of OH-NHC on Au (111) due to the more inert nature of the Au surface.

Fig. 2 XPS (a-b) and polarized NEXAFS (c-d) measurements of OH-NHCs on Pt (111). (a) N1s and (b) C1s XPS spectra, along with (c) Nitrogen k-edge and (d) Carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra were measured before (spectra i, black colored) and after annealing of the NHC-coated sample to 200 °C (spectra ii, blue colored). P- and s-polarized NEXAFS spectra were marked by solid and dotted lines, respectively.

The C1s XPS signal of OH-NHCs on Pt (111) surface (Fig. 2b, spectrum i) displayed a comparable peak pattern to the one obtained on Au (111). The three Gaussians that constructed the C1s XPS signal were attributed to C–C, C–N/C–O and C=O species. Analysis of the potassium XPS peak area revealed that the amount of potassium on Pt (Fig. 2b, spectrum i) is three-fold higher than that detected on Au (Fig. 1b, spectrum i). The partial decomposition of surface-anchored molecules and higher surface concentration of potassium were both correlated to stronger interaction with the reactive Pt surface. In fact, strong chemisorption on Pt has been reported for both benzene^{44,45} and polyconjugated hydrocarbons⁴⁶ which were found to stay flat on Pt (111).

Nitrogen k-edge NEXAFS spectra of the as deposited OH-NHCs on Pt (111) exhibited two main peaks located at 399.5 and 401.5 eV, related to aromatic N1s→ π^* _{Imidazole} and to imidazole N1s→ π^* _{Imidazoline} transitions, respectively (Fig. 2c, spectrum i). An additional shoulder was located at 398.8 eV and attributed to a decomposition species. The position of this peak indicates that C–N bond cleavage has occurred in some of the surface anchored molecules.²⁹ This shoulder was not detected when the OH-NHCs were anchored on Au (111). Carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra of the as-deposited OH-NHCs on Pt (111) displayed a noticeable shoulder at 289.4 eV, correlated to C1s→ π^* _(C=O) transition (Fig. 2d, spectrum i). The detection of this feature suggests that oxidation of the hydroxyl groups occurred upon surface-anchoring of OH-NHCs on Pt (111).

Carbon and nitrogen NEXAFS spectra showed mild dichroism for OH-NHCs that were anchored on Pt (111), in comparison to the one detected on Au (111) (Scheme 2). The shoulder that was detected in the nitrogen NEXAFS spectra at 398.8 eV and attributed to a decomposition species showed high degree of dichroism and was mostly obtained in the p-polarized spectrum. On the other hand, the two peaks in the nitrogen NEXAFS spectra that were located at higher energy (399.5 and 401.5 eV) showed higher intensity in the s-polarized spectrum. These results reveal the presence of two subpopulations of OH-NHCs on Pt surface. One sub-population is positioned

flat-lying on the surface and strongly interacts with the Pt substrate. The strong electronic interaction between the nitrogen atoms in the flat-lying OH-NHCs and the Pt surface can induce the shift in the peak position³⁴ and/or partial decomposition of the C-N bonds in the imidazoline ring.²⁰ The second subpopulation is characterized with some preference of the imidazoline ring toward a standing orientation, leading to weaker interaction with the Pt substrate and therefore less prone for decomposition.

The minor dichroism in the σ^* region (290-295 eV) of the carbon k-edge spectrum (Fig. 2d, spectrum i) indicates a preferred flat-lying orientation of the wingtip groups. The overall lower level of dichroism of OH-NHCs on Pt (111), in comparison to the one detected on Au (111), can be correlated to the strong interaction between the OH-NHCs and the Pt surface. This interaction circumvented the diffusion of OH-NHCs on the metal surface, which is essential for the formation of an ordered SAM. The lower level of dichroism for NHCs on Pt (111) can be also linked with higher surface concentration of potassium that limited the formation of a well-ordered SAM. It was previously demonstrated that sub-monolayer of potassium can influence the properties of adsorbates on metal surfaces.^{47,48}

The N1s/Au4f, N1s/Pt4f, C1s/Au4f and C1s/Pt4f XPS peaks area ratios were analysed in order to identify if the cause for the variations in the anchoring geometry of OH-NHCs on Pt and Au is due to differences in their surface density (Supp. Info. Fig. S1-S3).^{49,50} The comparative analysis revealed that the N1s/Au4f peaks area ratio was higher by 15% than the N1s/Pt4f peaks area ratio. These results show that there are relatively minor variations in the surface density of OH-NHCs on the two metals. Thus, the higher orientational order of OH-NHCs on Au surface cannot be linked with higher surface density of NHCs but more likely to be correlated with weaker metal-adsorbate interactions that enabled improved diffusion of NHCs on the Au surface.

A decrease of 50 and 65 % in the peaks area of N1s and C1s XPS signals, respectively, were obtained following annealing of the OH-NHCs on Pt (111) to 200 °C (Fig. 2a and 2b, spectrum

ii). The changes in the peaks area were linked to desorption of OH-NHCs from the surface. The decrease in the N1s and C1s XPS peaks area was more significant for OH-NHCs that were anchored on Pt than on Au. This difference can be connected to the lower level of dichroism in the self-assembled molecules on Pt (111) that limited the formation of stabilizing intermolecular interactions.

Annealing of the OH-NHCs on Pt (111) prompted a change in the peak pattern of the nitrogen k-edge spectra (Fig. 2c, spectrum ii). A decrease was detected in the amplitudes of the NEXAFS peaks located at 398.8 and 401.5 eV, while the amplitude of the central peak at 399.5 eV was increased. These changes indicate that imidazoline ring dehydrogenation was facilitated following surface annealing (Scheme 1).⁵¹ Dichroism analysis showed a minor preference toward a standing orientation of the imidazoline ring of the NHCs. The carbon k-edge NEXAFS spectra displayed an increase in the intensity of the $\pi^*_{(C=N)}$ transition (285 eV) after annealing (Fig. 2d, spectrum ii), correlated to dehydrogenation of the imidazoline backbone and aromatization of the carbene ring. The annealing-induced chemical changes were not coupled with a major change in the dichroism of OH-NHCs on Pt (111). The spectroscopic data revealed that annealing-induced dehydrogenation and aromatization were more pronounced for OH-NHCs that were anchored on Pt, in comparison to those anchored on Au. This is possibly due to the reactive nature of the Pt surface that effectively facilitated the dehydrogenation-aromatization reaction.⁵²

Conclusions

The anchoring geometry, thermal stability and chemical reactivity of self-assembled OH-NHCs on Au (111) and Pt (111) were analysed. Oxidation of the OH groups along with dehydrogenation of the imidazoline backbone, which induced ring aromatization, were detected in the as-deposited OH-NHCs. The dehydrogenation-aromatization reactions were facilitated on Pt (111) and

coupled with partial decomposition of the surface-anchored OH-NHCs. Preference toward a flat-lying position was detected for OH-NHCs on Au (111), while no preference for specific anchoring geometry was obtained for OH-NHCs on Pt (111). Annealing of the surface-anchored OH-NHCs led to partial desorption and increased the dehydrogenation-aromatization reaction within the surface-anchored molecules. An increase in the dichroism was obtained following annealing of the OH-NHCs on Au (111), while no annealing-induced changes in the dichroism were detected for OH-NHCs on Pt (111). It can be therefore concluded that the stronger interaction between OH-NHCs and Pt surface induced higher reactivity and lower level of dichroism on Pt (111), in comparison to Au (111). The lower levels of dichroism for OH-NHCs on Pt surface can be correlated as well to higher surface concentration of potassium that limited the formation of a well-ordered monolayer. The spectroscopic measurements therefore demonstrate the crucial influence of metal-adsorbate interactions on the anchoring-geometry and chemical reactivity of addressable OH-NHC SAMs.

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